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**How do science and engineering students approach revisions?
A self-regulated learning tool for supporting the transition from secondary to
higher education.**

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INTRODUCTION

Transition from secondary school to higher education is an issue worldwide [1]. For students, part of the struggle in staying in higher education is to adapt their study skills from those that were effective in a highly supported secondary school environment to the more autonomous environment of higher education. As an example, students integrating an engineering curriculum need to adopt a methodological approach allowing them to solve problems previously unseen, where the solution method needs to be created by the student [2]. Actually, in order to make this transition from secondary school to engineering education, students will not only need to develop their learning strategies but more importantly their capacity for self-regulated learning.

Self-regulated learning is defined as involving self-generated thoughts, feelings, and actions that are systematically guided by personal goals [3]. Actions, for example, include planning, monitoring and evaluating, behaviours that students display when they study. Students who, when solving a mathematical problem, start by analysing the problem and making a plan are demonstrating self-regulated learning behaviours. Students who, when revising, clarify what they need to learn and then chose revision techniques which are directed towards these learning goals are also demonstrating self-regulated learning behaviours. Alongside these behaviours self-regulated learning also involves a particular pattern of thinking in which the learner will mentally monitor their own progress on learning and adapt their strategies as appropriate [4].

Students can be helped to develop self-regulated learning and training for self-regulated learning has been in place for many years. Panadero, Klug and Järvelä have recently argued that one interesting area for development is the use of measurement tools for self-regulated learning as intervention tools [5]. Thought of in this way, the process of reflecting on one's self-regulated learning, through undertaking a task such as a learning diary or a self-report questionnaire can trigger students to adapt their practices. This has already have some positive results, see Schmitz and Perels [6].

In order to help engineering students develop their self-regulated learning skills, we aimed to develop a self-report questionnaire which could be used as a feedback and intervention tool with students. The questionnaire was developed based on three evidence-informed learning strategies. In collaboration with a physics teacher in a secondary school, the questionnaires have been administered to a large cohort of science and engineering students in both higher education and secondary school settings, and was tested for factorial validity and reliability. The results of this questionnaire development process are reported on in this paper.

1 RELATED WORK

When reaching higher education, students have succeeded thanks to their study habits until this point. However, many do not realise they need to adapt those habits to this new context (until they eventually fail, after one or even two semesters). Therefore, helping students to make the transition from secondary to higher education

requires first to make them think about how they learn. The questionnaire and associated feedback is designed so that students have to review and reflect on their study habits. By developing their metacognitive abilities, this questionnaire aims at making students become progressively self-regulated learners [7]. As a number of meta-analyses have shown that teaching self-regulated learning has an positive impact on student attainment [8], this, in it-self, can help students succeed.

A study habit that students need to adapt when integrating an engineering college is revisions. A survey of around 600 students at the Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) has shown that the two techniques they use most frequently are a) re-read their course notes and b) re-do exercises. Strikingly, Dunlosky et al. have shown that re-reading is among the revision techniques frequently used by students which are ineffective [9]. Therefore, the questionnaire presented in this paper aims at making students aware of the revision techniques they use simply by force of habit and making them conscious that there exist more effective revision techniques.

We have selected three categories of revision techniques shown to have a reasonable impact on achievement across disciplines and assessment formats, without requiring specific training: elaboration, organization and retrieval. In elaboration techniques, learners identify the connections among pieces of information and actively relate new knowledge to prior knowledge. Concept mapping is one of these [10]. In organization techniques, learners select and structure important points in the material to study. Summarization is an example of an organization technique (whose effectiveness typically varies depending on the quality of the produced summaries [11]). In a more recent study [12], Karpicke and Blunt have shown that the third category of revision techniques called “retrieval practice” gives remarkable results and even outperforms concept mapping for instance. In retrieval practice, students reconstruct knowledge by trying to recall information (using cues or not) instead of trying to re-memorize it.

To be able to provide students with instant and individual feedback on the revision techniques they use, we chose to implement a self-reporting questionnaire. Despite relying on students to accurately report their own work, self-reporting questionnaires such as the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) [4] have shown good reliability and validity with reasonable correlations with attainment. Simple to implement and to use in autonomy by students, self-reporting questionnaires help promote self-regulated learning. In the following, we present the structure of the questionnaire and report how it was administered to students.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire consists of eleven items where students rate to which extent an affirmative statement corresponds to their study habits on a seven-point Likert scale. The items form three subscales corresponding to the three categories of revision techniques presented earlier: A-Relate information, B-Organise information and C-

Practice recall. Four items are borrowed from the MSLQ. We had to design the other items as retrieval practice was not covered by the MSLQ and the questions also had to match the study context of our students. Examples of questions are: for subscale A “I try to see how exercises relate to real life applications.” (Q3), for subscale B “When I study for this course, I write short summaries with the most important points.” (Q4) and for subscale C “I try to test myself to see if I can remember the key ideas of the course.” (Q8). The questionnaire has been kept short on purpose, since its first and foremost goal is to be a quick feedback tool for students.

2.2 Data collection

A paper based data collection phase has been organized in the middle of the spring semester² in four classes of first year engineering bachelor (hereafter called BA1, N = 346), with students from seven science and engineering departments. In addition, a group of students who had failed their autumn semester and were attending a reboot semester during the spring were also included in the study (BA1-Reboot, N = 31).

In parallel, the questionnaire has been administered to four different classes of secondary students in the context of a physics course given by the same teacher. Three classes are from the lower senior cycle in fundamental sciences (SEC-Low, N = 80). One class is from the upper senior cycle (SEC-Up, N = 21) with a specialization in physics and applied maths. The students taking this specialization are typically intending to undertake studies in engineering, science or medicine.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Reliability and validity

We carried out a Principal Component Analysis, which indicated that the emergent factor structure matched the three proposed subscales. However, some questions had low reliability scores affecting the reliability of the scale. After the exclusion of two questions, Cronbach’s alpha for the different subscales ranges from .62 (subscale A-Relate information) to .69 (subscale B-Organise information). As a result, the questionnaire counts nine questions (three questions per subscale). Cortina and Schmitt both identify that the alpha is associated with the number of test items and so a scale with a small number of test items may well have an alpha lower than the typically cited cut off of .7 [13, 14]. Such scales can be reported, however with the caveat that reliability is questionable. In line with practice in other tests, we propose that it is acceptable to use these scales for reflection purposes but that they would need further development to be accepted as a reliable measure. The following sections present the quantitative results obtained with the questionnaire.

3.2 Overall scores

The mean score over the questionnaire, all groups included, is $M = 4.30$, $SD = .925$ on a scale of seven. Table 1 and Fig. 1 report the detail of the overall score for the

² The data collection has been managed by a group of master students as part of their project in a course on learning sciences during the spring semester.

different groups. It is interesting to notice that the score obtained by students attending the reboot semester is the lowest of all groups. In particular, it is lower than that of the students attending the standard engineering curriculum even if the difference is not significant, $t(375) = -1.76, p = .08$. This may indicate that these students, who have failed their autumn semester, are less likely to use effective revision techniques.

Group	N	M	SD
SEC-Low	80	4.39	.914
SEC-Up	21	4.44	.701
BA1	346	4.30	.929
BA1-Reboot	31	3.99	.999
Total	478	4.30	.925

Table 1. Overall score per group

Fig. 1. Score distribution per group

3.3 Relate information (subscale A)

Fig. 2 presents the mean score per subscale for the different groups. On subscale A-Relate information, engineering students score significantly lower than secondary students, $t(476) = -3.09, p < .01$. More specifically, BA1 students score significantly lower than SEC-Up students, $t(365) = -2.19, p = .03$. A possible reason for such a difference is that the physics teacher in the secondary classes coaches his students on the use of the different resources he makes available for his class [15]. Therefore, these students might have specifically developed their ability at relating information from different sources compared to other secondary students.

Fig. 2. Mean score per subscale and per group

Fig. 3. Mean score per question

As Fig. 3. illustrates, question 3 stands out as having a particularly low mean score in subscale A, and again bachelor students score significantly lower than secondary students on this question, $t(474) = -3.77, p < .001$. Interestingly, this question

assesses whether students try to identify how exercises relate to real life applications. An important factor here might lie in the nature of the core courses in the propaedeutic year of the bachelor of engineering. Transversal to all departments and generally given by professors from the School of Basic Sciences, these courses are designed to introduce the formalisms necessary in the following years. Aiming at developing students' abstraction, some of these courses include few examples of applications. Students would then have to work them out by themselves.

3.4 Organise information (subscale B)

The mean score on subscale B-Organise information ($M = 3.81$, $SD = 1.44$) is the lowest of all three subscales, and the difference is significant when comparing with subscales A and C. The particularly low mean scores on questions 5 and 6 (see Fig. 3) are interesting to consider. While question 4 assesses whether students write summaries of the course content, question 5 tests whether they outline the content of course resources and question 6 tests whether they use some kind of schematics to represent how information is organised. This could tend to indicate that while summarizing is a frequently used technique for students, they seem not to use more elaborated techniques to organise information.

Among bachelor students, the BA1-Reboot students score significantly lower than the BA1 group, $t(375) = -1.96$, $p = .05$. The context does not provide information to explain this result. It is possible that these students (who have failed their first semester), have a weak ability to organise information and that this might be a factor in their failure.

3.5 Practice recall (subscale C)

We found the mean score on subscale C-Practice recall ($M = 4.44$, $SD = 1.25$) to be higher than expected given the preference of students on rereading over other revision techniques. Secondary students from the upper cycle obtain the best score on this subscale ($M = 4.79$, $SD = 1.38$), although the difference with the other groups is not significant. Bachelor students in reboot semester score again lowest.

One possible hypothesis to explain the relatively high score on this subscale, in particular in the case of the engineering students, is that students practice a lot redoing exercises and consider it as a recall activity. A question is whether they maximise their practice of recall in that context. Because two of the questions are framed using the term "I try to (recall / test myself) ...", it is not possible to evaluate how long students persist in recalling information before checking their notes or looking up information. Data collected on campus shows, for instance, that when the solution of an exercise is available, many students look at the solution right away when they have a difficulty during the resolution (actually, a non-negligible proportion of students even tends to look at the solution before trying to solve the exercise).

4 DISCUSSION

Our goal is to help engineering students to develop self-regulated learning skills by developing a self-report reflection tool. The data suggests that we have made progress

towards developing such a tool. The results obtained by the secondary and bachelor groups, albeit on a non-random sample, show similar tendencies on lowest and highest subscales and items as well as clear differences between populations.

Of course, as for all self-reporting questionnaires, the conclusions have to be taken carefully as students' response might not accurately reflect their actual practices. On one hand, self-report measures are widely used and show good reliability and validity, but on the other hand, we know that students have difficulties assessing their own learning practices. However, this is not a major concern since the purpose here is to develop a tool for self-reflection, not to objectively measure learning practices.

One limitation regarding this study is that the secondary students are all from the same secondary school and have the same physics teacher. Our hypothesis was that first year engineering students use the study skills they have developed in high school but the results of our study tend to show a difference. It is well possible that these secondary students are not representative of secondary students in Switzerland, in particular because of the specific instructional methods of their physics teacher.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

We have developed a self-report questionnaire to help engineering students to develop self-regulated learning skills, specifically in the area of regulation of study (revision techniques). The results of the test phase presented in this paper show that the tool has factorial validity and is moving towards reliability. We conclude that it is suitable for self-reflection, while not yet a reliable measure. Further development is necessary, in particular the design of additional questions in subscales to enhance the overall reliability. In a preliminary phase, we have used this tool in different self-regulated learning interventions with personalized feedback for both secondary students and engineering students. A MOOC with videos, quizzes and reflective activities has been put in place to provide students with evidence-based support for the different study skills. We are currently developing a web-based "learning companion" integrating different self-regulated learning questionnaires with the MOOC resources.

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